

Hesychastic Controversy

also known as “Hesychasm, Palamism”

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Entry tags: Mysticism, Orthodoxy, Christian Mysticism, Orthodox Christianity, Christian Traditions, Orthodoxy, Orthodox/Eastern Christian, Greek Orthodox, Religious Group

The hesychast controversy which lasted for some two decades started as a theological dispute but evolved into a political matter, relating to the strife between the contenders of the Byzantine throne. Hesychasm was a method of monastic prayer and contemplation practiced in quietude, in “hesychia” in Greek, and thus the name hesychasm. The term designates the process of retiring inward by ceasing to register the senses, in order to achieve an experiential knowledge of God. The term “Hesychasm” was originally used in the 4th century to denote any kind of hermit or anchorite monk. Evagrius Ponticus or Evagrius the Solitary (345-399 AD), a disciple of Basil of Caesarea, was the first to systematize the various contemplative practices into a unified system of prayer. He explained what the act of praying is, and what its effect is on the individual. The goal of monasticism was not to proclaim the Kingdom of God through a particular kind of material existence but to attain the total disembodiment of the mind through prayer. Proper activity of the mind is to detach itself from the body so it can be united to God. Ps. Macarius (a conventional designation of the anonymous author of works falsely attributed to Macarius of Egypt, 300-391 AD) made Evagrius’s ideas more compatible with Orthodox teaching. He shifted the focus of contemplative prayer away from the mind and its detachment from the body and located the Incarnation as the focal point for contemplative prayer. According to Ps. Macarius, the presence of the incarnated God meant that God had become accessible through physical reality. By attaining what Ps. Macarius called “purity of heart,” one can enter into the eschatological reality of Christ’s presence in our mind, body, and spirit. This mystical method was centered around unceasing prayer that opened the monk to the way Christ was present in him. The monastic practices in question became a crucial subject of debate following the reaction towards the teachings of Barlaam of Calabria, or Barlaam of Seminara, who attacked them. Barlaam (1290-1348) was an Orthodox monk on Mount Athos. He was educated in the West, and he was a supporter of humanistic renaissance thinking. He was a faithful proponent of Orthodoxy. In the early 1330s, Barlaam met the monks of Mount Athos and doubted about their hesychastic method of prayer. The monks he met were poorly educated-if not completely illiterate and therefore unable to answer his questions about their practices. After this encounter, Barlaam insisted that their use of the human body in prayer and their direct experience of God was misguided and heretical. He wrote treatises condemning their practices, mocking the bodily positions involved during Hesychastic prayer. He rejected their claim to bodily awareness of the divine presence and their visions of the un-created light. He was concerned that these visions, if they were occurring, were not affecting the monks in ways he thought they should. The reaction to Barlaam’s opinions was headed mainly by the monk - and later bishop of Thessaloniki - Gregory Palamas (1296-1357/9), who became the main representative of hesychasm and the leader of the hesychast party. In 1341 Andronikos III Palaiologos summoned a Council which didn’t reach a conclusion. Following the emperor’s death, a civil war broke out between John Kantakouzenos and the supporters of the underage heir John V, concerning his succession. Kantakouzenos supported Palamas but so did his opponents, Alexios Apokaukos and Anna of Savoy. The aristocrats supported Palamas largely due to their conservative and anti-Western tendencies as well as their links to the Orthodox monasteries. It was not until the triumph of Kantakouzenos in taking Constantinople in 1347 that the Palamists were able to achieve a lasting victory over the anti-Palamists. The Council of 1351, summoned by the usurper John VI Kantakouzenos (reg. 1347-1354), recognised hesychasm as an official doctrine of the Orthodox Church, remaining thus until today.

Date Range: 1337 CE - 1351 CE

Region: Thessaloniki and Mount Athos.

Region tags: Europe, Greece, Eastern Europe, Macedonia, Thessaloniki, Mount Athos

Thessaloniki and Mount Athos, the main places where the Hesychasm and the Hesychastic controversy took place.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Saint Gregory Palamas, "Dialogue Between an Orthodox and a Barlaamite" (trans. R. Ferwerda), Binghampton University, New York.
- Source 2: Saint Gregory Palamas, "The One Hundred and Fifty Chapters" (trans. Robert Edward Sinkewicz), Pontifical Institute of Mediaeval Studies, 1988.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://bekkos.wordpress.com/martin-jugie-the-palamite-controversy/>
 - Source 1 Description: Martin Jugie : The Palamite Controversy
 - Source 2 URL: http://www.romanity.org/hm/rom.15.en.notes_on_the_palamite_controversy.01.htm
 - Source 2 Description: Notes on the Palamite Controversy and Related Topics
 - Source 3 URL: <https://web.archive.org/web/20110427171833/http://theandros.com/palamas.html>
 - Source 3 Description: Gregory Palamas on the Relationship Between Philosophy and Theology
- Notes: 1. http://www.oodegr.com/english/istorika/romi/hesychast_zealot1.htm Hesychasts and Zealots : Spiritual flourishing and social crisis in 14th century Byzantium 2. https://web.archive.org/web/20080803041114/http://www.monachos.net/library/Gregory_Palamas:_Knowledge,_Prayer,_a Gregory Palamas: Knowledge, Prayer and Vision 3. <https://bekkos.wordpress.com/juan-nadal-canellas-gregory-akindynoss-role-in-the-14th-century-hesychast-controversy/> Juan Nadal Cañellas : Gregory Akindynos's role in the 14th-century hesychast controversy 4. https://apostoliki-diakonia.gr/en_main/catehism/theologia_zoi/themata.asp?cat=hist&main=EH_texts&file=12.htm The Hesychasm in the Occident during the 14th Century

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://magnusinstitute.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/08/Gregory-of-Palamas-The-Triads.pdf>
- Source 1 Description: Gregory Palamas, Triads in Defence of the Holy Hesychasts
- Source 2 URL: https://www.agape-biblia.org/orthodoxy/Gregory_Palamas_The_Triads_Classics_of_Western_Spirituality.pdf
- Source 2 Description: Gregory Palamas, The Triads, translated by J. Meyendorff

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by class:

– Yes

Notes: The aristocrats supported hesychasm largely due to their conservative and anti-Western tendencies as well as their links to the Orthodox monasteries.

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– No

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– No

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– No

- ↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)
 - Yes

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

- Yes

- ↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:
 - Yes

- ↳ Apostates are socially shunned and/or publicly vilified:
 - Yes

- ↳ Wealth, civil rights, and/or social capital are taken by authorities:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Do apostates receive corporal punishment:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Do apostates receive divine punishment:
 - No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

- Field doesn't know

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

- Field doesn't know

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

- Large religious group (intolerant of other affiliations)

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

- No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Notes: When hesychasm became a universally accepted doctrine in 1375, art experienced substantial changes. The aim of this art was to contemplate transfigured flesh and matter, the shading of divine light, the fullness of ascent by the divine presence to ethereal heights. The main trend of the new style was a gradual shift away from painting expressing psychological states. Icons increased in size. Large images with full-length silhouettes were easy to read in the church's interior. Together with theological treatises and sermons, painted images expressed the essence of the doctrine of divine energy. The religious art used expressive colours that depicted high emotional states and also enhanced the mystical mood of the icon. The expression of the faces in these icons was more emotional than previously, depicting different mental states.

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– Only religious public space

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Yes

↳ Humans:

– Yes

↳

Other features of iconography:

– Yes

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– No

Notes: Quite the contrary. The hesychasts, by justifying the psycho-physical method of prayer, they reject the spiritualism of their opponent, Barlaam of Calabria. According to hesychasts, the body is far from being a prison of the soul, since the body itself receives the grace of the sacraments and the pledge of the final resurrection.

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳

Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

Notes: The main adversary of the hesychast movement, the monk Barlaam, advocated a rather non-spiritual and more rational theology that stood up in opposition against the hesychast methods of prayer. He believed that Hesychasm was simply unbelievable, not because there was no merit to what they were saying or that it was not rooted in Biblical or patristic sources, but because the hesychasts claimed that they were seeing God with their physical, sensible eyes, establishing thus a sort of communication through their own method of prayer. This, to hesychast adversaries, was the most absurd notion. According to Gregory Palamas, however, who defended hesychasm, the Kingdom of Heaven is something "within us." As such, the Second Coming is already a living reality for the Christian in his sacramental life and spiritual experience. This is justified both symbolically and also as something true and real in the life of the Christian, both monk and lay person. Palamas saw this as "supra-rational knowledge" which transcended any sort of rational argument, but was knowledge, and therefore communication, in the sense it was knowable by the senses and indeed something experienced by the practitioner of spiritual asceticism.

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– No

↳ In dreams:

– No

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

- ↳ Only through religious specialists:
 - No
- ↳ Only through monarch
 - No
- ↳ Other form of communication with living:
 - Field doesn't know

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

- No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

- No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

- No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

- No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Present and clear

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Hesychasts held that the acquisition of the unique experience requires strict methodical discipline and special organization of the entire existence of an ascetic, it requires the creation of a certain all embracing way of life, the "hesychast life". The hesychast life of necessity included ethical aspects: an ascetic's attitude to God and to his ascetic brethren, his attitude to the lay community he had left—all this was connected, directly and intimately, with ethical problems. The formation of the ascetic tradition necessarily involved the creation of a certain "inner ethics" of hesychasm. Instruction in prayer and spiritual concerns, moral pastorship, and giving advice on matters of daily life were its main aspects.

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:

– No

↳ Moral norms apply to:

– Only specialized religious class

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: It should be noted that by no means did Hesychasm and the hesychast way of life in general had the purpose to create a certain ethical system of their own. Hesychasm and hesychasts fully accepted the ethical norms of the New Testament presented in the Sermon on the Mount and in Christ's commandments. Moreover, ascetics believed that they ought to follow these precepts with far

greater rigor than mere laymen. Hesychast ethics can be viewed as a system of strictly personal salvation obtained through complete departure from earthly concerns and severance of all ties, through the intense and concentrated solitary work, which aimed at a total transformation of one's self. There have been accusations that this kind of ethics bore a significant individualistic slant, which nevertheless never gained complete dominance and was by no means the defining characteristic of hesychast ethics.

- ↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Courage (in battle):
 - No
- ↳ Courage (generic):
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:
 - Yes
- ↳ Generosity / charity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:
 - Yes
- ↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:
 - Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:
 - Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:
 - Yes
- ↳ Fidelity / loyalty:
 - Yes
- ↳ Cooperation:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– Yes

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Yes

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– No

↳ Strength (physical):

– No

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– No

↳ Humility / modesty:

– Yes

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– Yes

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Optimism / hope:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– Yes

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:

– Yes

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– Yes

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– Yes

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes [specify]: Admiration

Notes: Admiration is a complex compound in which love merges with compassion and wonderment; this is a very special kind of love, combining ethical and aesthetic aspects, which has its roots in hesychast asceticism. At the earliest stage of hesychasm admiration is normally mentioned alongside weeping and tears.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Notes: It should be noted, however, that although Hesychasm was primarily a monastic movement, its adherents were not exclusively monks.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily

alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Notes: However, the main opponent of Hesychasm, Barlaam of Calabria, attacked hesychasts by mocking them for their method of prayer. He nicknamed the Hesychasts "the navel-gazers". The nickname stems from the posture taken by the hesychast; omphaloscopy (i.e. gazing the navel) was the way to the search for the place of the heart. The teachers of this method advised that the hesychast should "sit down in a quiet cell, in a corner, close the door, and withdraw your intellect from everything worthless and transient. Rest your beard on your chest, and focus your physical gaze, together with the whole of your intellect, upon the centre of your belly or your navel".

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

Notes: Hesychasts stressed the necessity of a clean break with the earthly world. This separation had to be absolutely complete. The departure from mundane existence and lifestyle, was carried to extremes in early hesychasm, since the ascetic experience showed that spiritual advancement could be achieved only in this manner and an ascetic indeed could be with God and with men at the same time.

↳ To other in-group members:

– No

↳ To out-groups:

– No

↳ Destroyed:

– No

↳ Other:

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: The primary task of the hesychast is to engage in mental ascesis. The hesychast is to bring his mind into his heart so as to practice the Jesus Prayer with his mind in his heart. In solitude and retirement, the hesychast repeats the Jesus Prayer, "Lord Jesus Christ, son of God, have mercy on me, the sinner."

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:
– Field doesn't know

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):
Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.
– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.
– No

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– No

Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Field doesn't know

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Field doesn't know

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Field doesn't know

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

↳ Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– Yes

↳ Is such education open to both males and females:

– I don't know

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– I don't know

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other

than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:
– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:
– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:
– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:
– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:
– Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:
– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:
– Yes

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:
– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:
– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:
– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:
– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:
– Yes

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– I don't know

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

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